

SEX DETERMINATION IN *Daemonorops draco* USING RAPD METHOD

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Daemonorops draco or Rattan *Jernang* is a plant that has great potential for development. Indonesia is the largest exporter of jernang rubber in the world. Demand for Indonesian *jernang* sap from China is 400 tons-500 tons per year (Soemarna, 2009). This plant also has high economic value in Sumatra. However, the population is decreasing due to human activities, namely land conversion to rubber and oil palm plantations and illegal logging. Apart from that, the cultivation process is also difficult because the fruit is harvested when it is still young. So adult *D. draco* as the only source of seeds is not available (Asra et al., 2018). To support the development of the cultivation process, information is needed regarding the gender of *D.draco*. The Restriction Fragment length Polymorphism (RAPD) method can be used as a molecular marker in identifying sex in *D. draco*. There are several reasons why this theme is important to raise. First, an effort is needed to determine the sex of *D. draco* for cultivation purposes, one of which is by utilizing genetics and molecular science. Second, identification of molecular sex determination has never been carried out on *D. draco*. Third, the sex of *D. draco* plants has never been determined using the RAPD method as a molecular marker.

Previous research on *D. draco* has never discussed sex determination in this plant. Taxonomy, Morphology, Anatomy and Physiology are the fields of study that most discuss this plant. Genetic studies are still limited to information regarding genetic variations of *D. draco* using the ISSR and RAPD methods. Genetic diversity, relatedness, and identification of teasle gourd cultivars by RAPD markers was reported by Rasul et al., 2007. Rustiami et al (2004) explained the taxonomy and use of *Daemonorops draco* (Willd.) Blume. Asra et al (2014) explained the genetic diversity of *D. draco* with ISSR markers. Analysis of genetic diversity between populations can be made using genetic markers such as Random Amplified Polymorphic (RAPD) (Al-Khalifah et al., 2012). Several researchers have shown that random amplified polymorphic DNA (RAPD) banding patterns are linked to sex in plants such as *Carica papaya* (Urasaki et al., 2002) and Sequence characterized amplified regions (SCAR) markers have also been widely used to distinguish among the two sexes in *Asparagus officinalis* (Gao et al., 2007), *Carica papaya* (Bedoya et al., 2007), and *Rumex nivalis* (Stehlik and Blattner, 2004). RAPD is also used on several palm species such as *Pinanga javana* (Witono et al., 2006), *Elaeis guineensis* (Sathish & Mohankumar, 2007), *Phoenix dactylifera* (Younis et al., 2008; Haider et al., 2012; Al-Khalifah et al. al., 2012; Mirbahar et al., 2014; *Satakentia liukuensis* (Witono & Kondo, 2010).

D. draco is a type of palm that reproduces sexually by pollination. In female individuals of *D. draco* there are two flowers arranged together or dyads, consisting of one female flower and next to it there is one male flower with a smaller size. Based on the structure of the inflorescence, *D. draco* is

included in the androdioecious group, which consists of male individuals and hermaphroditic individuals (Asra et al., 2013). Knowledge of the sex of these individuals is important for understanding reproductive strategies in these populations. Identification of individuals who have male or female reproductive organs can influence strategies for maintaining genetic diversity in populations. For breeding purposes, it is very important to know hermaphroditic individuals known as females and male individuals so that appropriate treatment can be carried out.

Sex determination is the developmental decision that occurs during the plant life cycle that leads to the differentiation of two organs or cells that produce two gametes (Patil et al., 2012). Based on research conducted by Asra et al (2013), the event of Apomixis, namely the possibility of fruit formation if there is no pollen donor from individual male flowers, is possible. On the other hand, the unequal ratio of male and female individuals in *D. draco* in natural populations and the distribution of male individuals that are far from each other cause the plant to have a special strategy to survive. Therefore, based on the research gap that has been identified, sex determination in *D. draco* using the RAPD method can be implemented. Moreover, no previous research has discussed sex determination in *D. draco*. The advantages of using RAPD markers are: (1) a small quantity of DNA is needed, (2) low cost, (3) easy to learn, (4) primers are easily obtained, and (5) reveals a high level of polymorphism (Emoghene et al., 2015).

D. draco has high economic value in Sumatra, but the population has decreased due to land conversion and illegal logging, as well as difficulties in cultivation due to premature fruit harvest. Information about gender is important to support cultivation development, with RAPD as a potential molecular marker. Previous studies have not discussed sex determination of *D. draco* with RAPD. Further research is needed to understand its reproductive strategies and genetic diversity, especially the roles of male and female individuals. In my opinion, studies on other plants show the effectiveness of RAPD and SCAR in sex determination. Therefore, this research will analyze the sex determination of *D. draco* with RAPD to fill knowledge gaps and expand understanding of this plant.

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